

It is significant to note that certain compounds which exhibit anomalous paramagnetism with respect to temperature also show that Faraday-effect independent of temperature, for example (Mlle) Collet (*Compt. rend.*, 1926 183, 1031) observed that the paramagnetic susceptibility of KMnO_4 and $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ does not show any variation with temperature. Also Pillai (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1932, 6, 573) showed that Faraday-effect in these compounds is as well independent of temperature. One may, therefore, expect the rotation of the uranyl salts also not to be affected by temperature since their susceptibility does not show any variation under the conditions. This, however, is not a general rule, for there are substances like manganese chloride and cobalt nitrate which obey Weiss law but show a constant magneto-optical rotation over the range of temperature investigated. Work, however, on the effect of temperature on the magneto-optical rotation of uranyl salts is in progress. We are also studying the effect of addition of free acids of the magneto-optical rotation of these salts.

UNIVERSITY CHEMICAL LABORATORIES,
UNIVERSITY OF THE PUNJAB, LAHORE.

Received June 15, 1935.

The Anomalous Rotatory Dispersion of l - β Pinene. Part I.

By R. PADMANABHAN AND S. K. KULKARNI JATKAR.

In a previous work (Padmanabhan and Jatkar, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 56, 334) on the rotatory dispersion of seven isomeric hydrocarbons of the formula $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}$, the interesting observation that the optical rotatory power of d -sabinene passes through a maximum at about λ 3300 Å was made. Since d -sabinene and l - β -pinene are the only substances having anomalous rotatory dispersion known up till now among the optically active hydrocarbons, we felt that further work was desirable in order to throw light upon the origin of the peculiar optical behaviour of these compounds.

The optical rotatory power of l - β -pinene is negative in the visible region of the spectrum, the magnitude changing but slightly with wave-length, becomes zero at about λ 3700 Å and attains high positive values on the shorter wave-length side. This anomalous behaviour was first noticed by Darmsis (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1911, 22, 495) and although both he and quite recently, Servant (*Compt. rend.*,

1932, 194, 368) have measured the rotatory dispersion in the visible and in the ultraviolet, they have not attempted to explain the origin of the anomaly. It is not evidently due to the Cotton-effect, since an examination of the substance in alcoholic solution by the Hartley-Baly method shows the absence of any absorption in the anomalous region.

If we compare the formula of sabinene and β -pinene, it will be observed that both the compounds are characterised by the presence of a semicyclic double bond adjacent to an asymmetric carbon atom. According to Lowry and Walker (*Nature*, 1924, 115, 365) chromophoric groups when coupled sufficiently closely to an asymmetric complex can exhibit an induced asymmetry, as a result of which they may themselves become optically active. The semicyclic double bond has also been known to have a powerful influence on the refractive dispersion (Wallach, *Annalen*, 1908, 360, 34; Auwers and Ellinger, *ibid.*, 1912, 387, 200). Since induced asymmetry need not always lead to an optical rotation of the same sign as that of the fixed asymmetric groups by which it is controlled, it appeared as if the proximity of the double bond to an asymmetric carbon atom were responsible for the anomaly. However camphene (Padmanabhan and Jatkar *loc. cit.*) which also possesses the same characteristics does not show any signs of anomalous rotatory dispersion up to 3100Å.

It seemed probable that the presence of a *dextro*-rotatory second component having a different rotatory dispersive power and which is separable from β -pinene only with great difficulty might give rise, by superposition of the two rotatory dispersions, to this anomaly in the region of transparency. Nopinene (β -pinene) is one of the most commonly occurring among the terpenes, being almost always associated with α -pinene in many turpentine oils and has been isolated by several workers (Dupont, *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1924, i, 10, 184; Austerweil, *Chim. Industrie, special no.*, 1926, 603). Nevertheless the simultaneous occurrence of closely related substances and the tendency so common among the terpenes to distil together in spite of a difference in boiling point of several degrees, made it seem probable that even if nopinene were really heterogenous it might have escaped notice by previous workers. Although this expectation has not been realised, our work makes it clear that elaborate purification—much more than what is usually attempted in most of the work on terpenes—is necessary in order to free β -pinene from associated impurities.

Purification and Darmois Diagram.

Unfortunately no crystalline derivative of nopinene is known from which the parent hydrocarbon could be regenerated so that only physical methods like fractional distillation are available for purification. A commercially available pure sample of nopinene was, therefore, fractionally distilled in a very efficient rectifying column. The practically constant boiling point (62°/21 mm.) of the starting material would lead one to the belief that it was homogenous but by the maintenance of a suitable reflux ratio and by the systematic addition of each fraction when nearly half the previous fraction had distilled over, and by carrying out the distillation in an atmosphere of dry carbon dioxide to prevent the formation of oxidation products, it was found that after nine redistillations there was a gradual transition from a *laevo*-rotatory substance in the first fraction to a *dextro*-rotatory substance of higher rotatory dispersive power in the last, both having normal dispersion in the visible spectrum (normal only in the sense that rotation increases with decreasing wave-length). This appears to point to the conclusion that the various fractions are but mixtures in varying proportion of these two compounds and that the anomalous R. D. of the middle fractions is due to the superposition of the rotatory dispersions of these substances. The heterogenous nature of nopinene is thus rendered plausible by these results but it was noticed that they could also be explained if we postulate the occurrence along with nopinene in the turpentine oil from which it was isolated, a *laevo*-rotatory constituent of lower boiling point and a less volatile *dextro*-rotatory constituent. In order to decide between these two possible alternatives, the rotations of the various fractions for the wave-lengths 5780Å and 4358Å were represented on a Darmois diagram (Darmois, Thesis de Doctorate, Paris, 1910) which permits one to recognise whether there are two or more than two optically active substances in a mixture. If we consider a mixture of two substances whose specific rotatory powers are (α_1) and (α_2) while x and $1-x$ are the proportion in which they occur, the specific rotatory power of the mixture $[\alpha] = x [\alpha_1] + [1-x] [\alpha_2]$ from this one gets the relation,

$$\frac{1-x}{x} = \frac{[\alpha_1] - [\alpha]}{[\alpha] - [\alpha_2]}$$

In Fig. 1 if OA_1 , OB_1 , and OC_1 , represent for a wave-length, λ_1 , the specific rotatory powers of the two pure substances and the

mixture respectively, it follows from the above relation that the ratio C_1A/C_1B is independent of the wave-length. Hence if A_2 , B_2 and C_2 are the corresponding points for another wave-length λ_2 , A_1A_2 , B_1B_2 and C_1C_2 must be concurrent. Conversely, if a mixture is resolved into fractions whose dispersions could be represented by such a diagram it should contain only two components.

FIG. 1.

Darmois diagram.

FIG. 2.

Darmois diagram of β -pinene fractions.

Applying this to the case of β -pinene (Fig. 2), it is evident from the figure that there are three substances involved, the head and the tail fractions representing two component mixtures of a *laevo* and a *dextro*-rotating compound respectively with β -pinene isolated in a practically pure form in the middle fractions and having anomalous rotatory dispersion. The origin of the anomaly cannot, therefore, be explained away by attributing it to the presence of an impurity.

Raman spectra.—Further support for this conclusion is furnished by a study of the Raman-effect of the head, middle and tail fractions. The data are tabulated in Table I. It can be observed that a number of frequencies occurring as strong lines in the head and tail fractions does not occur even as faint lines in the middle fraction and *vice versa*. This cannot be explained if we assume that the middle fraction is a mixture and on purification is splitting up into its components. The citrus like odour of the last fraction and the previous observation of Dupont and Barrand (*Bull. Inst. Pin.*, 1928, 45, 76) that β -pinene from *Pinus Maritima* is associated with limonene and dipentene led us to compare the Raman spectra of the two substances with that of

the last fraction but no resemblance whatsoever was found. The Raman spectra of pure β -pinene will be discussed in a subsequent communication. It is not however out of place to point out the fact that the long shifts ignored by Dupont are very characteristic of the terpenes.

FIG. 3.
Rotatory dispersion of β -pinene fractions.

Curves I—III refer to head, middle and tail fractions respectively.

Rotatory dispersion of β -pinene.—The rotatory dispersions of the three fractions were determined by an improved method to be published shortly. The results are given in Table II. As seen from Fig. 3., the head fraction is contaminated with an appreciable percentage of β -pinene, the anomalous rotatory dispersion of which makes itself felt in the region of shorter wave-lengths. The high rotatory dispersive power of the tail fraction can likewise be attributed to the same cause. The rotatory dispersion curve of the middle fraction which is

taken as representing that of a fairly pure sample of β -pinene does not differ appreciably from those given by the two previous workers, Darmois and Servant in the longer wave-lengths, but the second anomaly reported by the latter at λ 2830 Å (*loc. cit.*) has not been confirmed by us although our measurements extend up to 2780 Å. We are attempting to extend the measurements further into the ultraviolet by using a hydrogen discharge tube as the light source.

EXPERIMENTAL.

500 G. of a sample of β -pinene (Schuchardt) of the following rotation in the visible $\alpha_{589} = -16.8$, $\alpha_{578} = -17.1$, $\alpha_{546} = 18.2$, $\alpha_{436} = 18.8$, were dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate and distilled over sodium under reduced pressure using a Widner-Schenck fractionating column. Eight fractions were obtained having the following rotations :

Fraction ...	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
α_{578} ...	-21.7	-20.6	-20.5	-19.6	-19.2	-17.8	-15.9	-6.6

The temperature was constant (62°/21 mm.) practically throughout the distillation. These were then redistilled in order, a fraction being added when nearly half the previous fraction had distilled over. After four such redistillations the following values were obtained for the consecutive fractions.

Fraction ...	33	34	35	36	37	38
α_{578} ...	-26.7	-25.0	-24.6	-21.5	-21.0	-20.7
Fraction ...	39	40	41	42	43	44
α_{578} ...	-20.0	-19.3	-18.7	-17.6	-13.5	-1.9

The separation though gradual is quite perceptible. The purification was, therefore, continued, and to have a better insight into the progress of the separation, the rotation for the three wave-lengths 5780, 5461, 4358 were measured. After three redistillations, the values were as follows.

TABLE I.

Fraction No.	α_{578} .	α_{546} .	α_{436} .	Fraction No.	α_{578} .	α_{546} .	α_{436} .
84	-29.3	-32.5	-48.0	92	-19.1	-20.2	-19.8
85	-26.2	-28.9	-39.6	93	-18.8	-20.0	-19.1
86	-24.7	-26.9	-35.1	94	-18.7	-19.7	-18.8
87	-23.7	-25.8	-32.4	95	-18.3	-19.4	-18.4
88	-23.0	-25.0	-30.7	96	-17.5	-18.5	-17.1
89	-21.9	-23.7	-27.5	97	-14.5	-15.2	-12.5
90	-20.3	-21.7	-23.1	98	+ 8.3	+ 9.7	+ 24.9
91	-19.4	-20.6	-20.6	99	+ 22.3	+ 25.9	+ 48.4.

Further purification was not attempted since the fractions 92-95 had nearly equal rotations and dispersions. The Darmois diagram of these fractions are represented in Fig. 2.

Raman Spectra.

The Raman spectra were obtained with a Fuess spectrograph having a dispersion $28\text{\AA}/\text{mm}$. Different exposures varying from 8-24 hours were given.

The wave-lengths of the Raman lines along with the shift in wave-numbers were measured. In order to bring out the differences in light scattering between the fractions, the shifts alone are tabulated separately (Table II).

TABLE II.

Comparative table showing the Raman spectra data.

Head fraction.	β -Pinene Middle fraction.	Tail fraction.	Dupont β -pinene.	Bonino l-Limonene.
301 (3)	296 (2b)			
335 (3)	327 (2b)	328 (2)		316 ($\frac{1}{2}$)
	385 (1b)	391 (2)	391 (1b)	435 (1)
	468 (2)	418 (2)	480 (2)	525 (1)
554 (4)	552 (3)	551 (4)		552 (1)
641 (3)	639 (5)	640 (4)	648 (5)	643 (0)
662 (3)	713 (1)	657 (4)		
761 (2)	761 (2)			765 (3)
	814 (2)		778 (2b)	802 (2)
	848 (4)		850 (5)	
	872 (4)	867 (1)	879 (5)	890 (1)
	923 (2)			916 (1)
948 (3)	949 (2)		942 (4b)	950 (1)
	1010 (3)			
	1045 (2)		1048 (3)	
	1096 (3)		1091 (1b)	
	1126 } (5b)		1134 (3)	
	1186 }			1168 (1)
	1214 (5b)		1224 (4b)	
1256 (3)	1254 (3)		1251 (2)	
	1298 } (2)	1308 (2)		1378 (2)
	1411 }			
1442 (3)	1432 (2b)	1428 (3)	1430 (8bb)	1446 (5)
		1616 (3)		
	1638 (5)	1634 (3)	1641 (10)	
1651 (3)		1668 (3)		1658 (3)
				1680 (3)
	2869 (1)			2860 (4)
2921 (3b)	2933 (2b)	2915 (3b)		2923 (4)
2985 (3b)	2987 (2)	2971 (3)		2973 (1)
3047 (3)		3047 (5)		
	3074 (4)			3082 (2)
3125 (3)		3126 (3)		
	3153 (4)			3156 (0)

TABLE III.

Rotatory dispersion of β -pinens.

Head fraction.		Middle fraction.				Tail fraction.	
Rotation.	λ .	Rotation.	λ .	Rotation.	λ .	Rotation.	λ .
-29.77	5893	-19.53	5893	33.5	3348	7.8	5893
-31.88	5730	-20.04	5780	38.9	3297	8.2	5780
-35.60	5461	-21.38	5461	46.6	3275	10.1	5461
-56.80	4358	-22.11	4358	54.4	3220	25.5	4358
-66.4	4078	-23.2	5100	57.9	3208	27.2	4297
-70.0	3920	-23.6	4893	65.6	3186	31.2	4134
-76.8	3775	-23.2	4735	72.5	3161	35.2	4017
-82.2	3638	-23.1	4584	102.0	3082	39.2	3932
-84.4	3525	-22.9	4147	123.2	3036	43.2	3866
-82.2	3408	-22.2	4342	147.2	2980	51.2	3709
-81.5	3325	-19.0	4090	174.8	2940	59.2	3580
-77.2	3214	-17.7	4010	204.0	2906	67.2	3540
-70.8	3103	-11.1	3781	231.6	2871	75.2	3452
-66.0	3012	-0.8	3644	260.0	2837	83.2	3378
		10.5	3535	288.4	2806	95.2	3305
		15.1	3472	319.6	2782	107.2	3223
		20.5	3420			119.2	3157
						135.2	3099

SUMMARY.

1. The rotatory dispersions of a pure sample of β -pinene till $\lambda 2780\text{\AA}$ and of the head and tail fractions have been measured by a modification of the usual photographic method. This has been found necessary on account of the smallness of the rotatory dispersion in the visible and near ultraviolet regions of the spectrum.

2. A prolonged purification by fractional distillations of a sample of the substance seems to indicate that the anomaly at 2800\AA reported by Servant is due to a closely associated impurity.

which is separable from β -pinene only with great difficulty. A Darmois diagram of the various fractions shows, however, that anomalous rotatory dispersion in the near ultraviolet still remains a characteristic of β -pinene. This conclusion is supported by Raman effect data of the various fractions obtained.

3. The anomalous rotatory dispersion of β -pinene is not due to Cotton-effect because there is no evidence of any absorption in the region of the anomaly. It must, therefore, be due to a superposition effect caused by a second rotation of opposite sign and having a different dispersion.

4. This second rotation cannot be attributed to the 'induced dissymmetry' of the semicyclic double bond because camphene which is also similarly constituted has been shown in a previous work to possess normal dispersion.

DEPARTMENT OF GENERAL CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF SCIENCE,
BANGALORE.

Received June 4, 1935.

Studies in the Cotarnine Series. Part IV.
5-Bromonarcotine, 5-Bromocotarnine, 5-Bromohydro-
cotarnine and 5-Bromonarceine and their Derivatives.

BY B. B. DEY AND T. K. SRINIVASAN.

The only references to literature about bromocotarnine and bromohydrocotarnine are to be found in two papers by Wright (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1877, **32**, 525) and by Heimann (Dissertation, Marburg, 1892, p. 15 ; also Small, "Chemistry of the Opium Alkaloids," 1932, pp. 68, 70, 98). Bromonarcotine and bromonarceine do not appear to have been prepared before.